

UK-Ireland Digital Humanities Association

Advocacy and Engagement Report 2025-26

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Executive Summary

The Digital Humanities (DH) community in the UK and Ireland has a wealth of practitioners and resources across universities (HEIs) and cultural heritage organizations (GLAM). As part of the inaugural Advocacy & Engagement Fellowship for the UK-IE DH Association, I surveyed the existing landscape and asked members of the community what would benefit them most in terms of community engagement and support. The recommendations for the Association and the DH community are as follows:

- **Support and expand existing DH infrastructures**, such as DARIAH's Course Registry and the Software Sustainability Institute's (SSI's) Collaborations Workshop, to reduce duplicating existing efforts.
- **Host virtual or regional events**, with particular focus on (1) networking events to support engagement between HEI and GLAM organizations and (2) workshops to share methodological and pedagogical best practices.
- **Engage with social media platforms** like LinkedIn to provide event awareness and highlight the existing network of practitioners.
- **Expand the fellowship programme and conference bursaries** to support early career researchers (ECRs) and their collaborative opportunities.
- **Provide collaborative small grants** which support research and stress collaboration between the UK and Ireland and/or HEIs and GLAM researchers.
- **Publish white papers** to highlight excellent research and support lobbying efforts in government, while providing writing opportunities for students and ECRs.

The subsequent report goes into greater detail on how and why these recommendations were reached.

Introduction and Background

The UK-Ireland Digital Humanities Association (henceforth referred to as 'the Association') was started in 2022 to help connect DH practitioners in the UK and Ireland. The Association's [core values](#) are:

- Inclusivity
- Community
- Collaboration
- Sustainability
- Openness and transparency
- Advocacy and action

In pursuit of the last value, the Association started an Advocacy and Engagement Fellowship to expand the understanding of community needs and possibilities for expanding the Association's outreach. Over the course of the fellowship, I took stock of the existing DH landscape in Ireland and the UK and talked to practitioners to see what value they'd like to see from the Association going forward.

A goal of this Fellowship was to help export the expansion of inclusion into the DH community in the region. However, this could only be accomplished with respect to the needs and interests of the existing community. Transparency is a key organizing principle for the Association; documents and plans are offered on collaborative platforms that highlight the process and comments around contributions in addition to the results. In keeping with this practice, while suggestions were modeled on various existing advocacy infrastructures, the recommendations were taken with gratitude from the DH community.

My priority was to find ways to expand the community of practitioners who felt the Association could support them. This was a twofold goal: **first**, to support students and early career researchers (ECRs) whose precarity in research organizations means that they may not see long-term community building as a valuable use of their time. And **second**, to better engage with and include practitioners from cultural heritage institutions (GLAM) within a community that

can at times seem focused on academic research at higher educational institutions (HEIs).

In order to achieve these goals, I undertook to:

- Speak with the organizers of the Association to learn about their priorities.
- Map the existing DH educational landscape to see when folks begin identifying with that label in Ireland and the UK.
- Survey DH community members virtually to ask directly what they'd like to see from the Association.
- Host a workshop at the Association's third annual event in Glasgow to discuss further advocacy opportunities.
- Interview volunteer survey respondents and related organizers to learn more about their recommendations and interests.
- Publish a proof-of-concept advocacy white paper on Prof. Sally Bushell's work on using Minecraft for literacy education at Lancaster University.
- Develop this report consolidating the preceding research and provide recommendations for the Association.

DARIAH and Existing DH Associations

The landscape of pre-existing DH organizations in the region is robust, however, they are often departmental or regionally focused. There's [CILIP](#), the UK's library and information professionals association, and [The Library Association of Ireland](#). There's the British [Museums Computer Group](#) (MCG) and the [Irish Museums Association](#) (IMA). Some organizations unaffiliated with DH still benefit disciplinary practitioners, such as the [Royal Historical Society](#), which supports digital historians or the [Society of Research Software Engineering](#), which supports research software engineers (RSEs). There are also overarching umbrella organizations like [Alliance of Digital Humanities Organizations](#) (ADHO), which seeks to unify different regional groups.

One such model of a mature DH advocacy organization is The Digital Research Infrastructure for the Arts and Humanities (DARIAH). Started in 2014 as a [European Research Infrastructure Consortium](#) (ERIC), the Infrastructure seeks to enhance and support digitally enabled research and teaching across the Arts and Humanities. It organises resources to share and preserve data and methods,

including hosting [OpenMethods](#), a blog with educational resources on digital tools and methodologies, although this has not been updated since 2024. [DARIAH Teach](#) provides teaching opportunities and resources. There are 24 member countries, including Ireland, and 10 cooperating partners, including institutions in the UK. DARIAH publishes a journal, *Transformations*, and hosts an Annual event to gather research and community.

The Advocacy and Outreach efforts of DARIAH are organised around their working groups, which provide services (e.g. DH Course Registry, Community Engagement) or focus around research interests (e.g. Multilingual DH, Women Writers in History). The Community Engagement working group was started in 2014 and uses an array of methods to support collaboration and community. They provide:

- Funding for an MPhil student intern and early career travel bursary
- Research funding for PhD training and workshops
- Publication of reports including the 2018 [Community Engagement Report](#) and the [2023 PhD Training Report](#)
- Hosted workshops and a webinar on barriers to engaging with research infrastructure
- Presenting research at non-DH conferences to expand research
- Book chapter in the *Routledge Handbook of Digital Humanities* (2019)

However, funding and community stability make ongoing engagement difficult. The Working Group first received funding in 2018, yet by 2024 they had already skipped events they had vowed to host around [PhD training](#).

While some of the DARIAH working groups are very active, others are effectively defunct. The Community Engagement group at DARIAH has not hosted events or updated their blog since 2024. The DH Course Registry has not included several Irish and British courses. As part of my fellowship, I have updated the course list to include more programmes in Ireland and the UK in the DARIAH registry, but durability remains a persistent issue.

Since groups are based on volunteer practitioner interest, and there is little motivation to update the resources at the pace of landscape evolution. This may be due to the lack of academic recognition or perceived value for engagement with research and community infrastructure, which can create [divides on](#)

[gendered lines](#). Alternatively, it may be that public communication methods like blogs are not well suited towards smaller or niche communities and that private communications are more active.

The Association's existing Community Interest Groups function in much the same way as DARIAH working groups. The Association [hosts community interest groups](#) (CIGs) of varying activity levels in: Research Software Engineering in the Arts and Humanities, DH Climate Coalition, Digital Correspondence, Multilingual DH in the UK and Ireland, and Protecting the Investigator in Traumatic Research Areas.

There are many DH organizations, like DARIAH, that support research and creative work within the discipline. But DARIAH's broad international remit and infrastructural focus leave more focused advocacy work to regional organizations. The opportunity for community structuring and organization across sectors and between the UK and Ireland is evidenced by the rapid growth of the Association. The question this report attempts to answer is how to provide meaningful value to potential members without duplicating existing work.

Feedback from the Community: Advocacy and Engagement Survey

In order to understand what people want to see from their Association, I conducted an online survey. The survey was hosted on SurveyMonkey and was open between May and August of 2025, with more than half of the responses collected in May. The purpose of the survey was to highlight advocacy opportunities for the Association, with particular goals of supporting inter-institutional collaboration and individual career growth for members of the DH community in the UK and Ireland. The survey was shared via online mailing lists and word of mouth.

The survey itself can be found in Appendix A, and the quantitative results can be found in Appendix B. The ethics of the survey and subsequent interviews were

approved by the research services team at the University of London (#SASREC_2425-1604-F).

The survey was designed in consultation with members of the Association's leadership, in light of feedback and suggestions from stakeholders at DARIAH and the Association. The options for Question 11 about skillsets were established by scraping the research and teaching skills listed on contemporary job applications in order to see how the DH 'market' aligns with the community. Three open Assistant Professor postings were analyzed: Digital and Computation Studies and History, Digital Humanities, and Digital Humanities and Film and Screen Studies. The variety of nomenclature mirrors the diversity of structures supporting DH work.

Survey Respondents

50 responses were then collected from participants who self-identified as members of the DH community. 38/50 respondents were based in the UK, with 10 based in Ireland and 2 based elsewhere (Question 4). 45/50 respondents indicated that they had an institutional home (Question 5), however when subsequently asked about the type of their primary institution, only one respondent indicated that they were not based at an HEI or GLAM (Question 6). This suggests some disconnect between the positionality results and the way that respondents identify, perhaps by aligning with previous university affiliations. 40 respondents (80%) were at HEIs, with 9 at GLAM institutions (18%) and 1 identifying as Other (2%) (Question 6). 23 respondents (46%) were affiliated with institutions in secondary capacities, including at Research Institutions and in Creative or Cultural Industry (Question 7). While not in the majority, it seems that many in the DH community have multiple homes. This is neither a strength nor weakness, as it could either lead to fragmentation, support more interdisciplinary work, or both.

There was good distribution in the survey responses across career stages (Question 12). 45/50 respondents answered the question, revealing a demographic breakdown that included 4 students (8.89%), 10 early career

professionals (22.22%), 22 mid-career professionals (48.89%) and 9 late career respondents (20%).

The overall trend featured results skewed towards HEIs and the UK, with proportionally fewer results from GLAM and Ireland. All Irish respondents were affiliated with HEI institutions, so the survey does not include insights from the Irish GLAM sector. While this limitation could be due in part to my own positionality (as a student at a British HEI), outreach attempts were made to make the Irish GLAM community aware of the survey. Targeted mailings were sent to the National Museum of Ireland, the National Gallery of Ireland, the National Library of Ireland, the Irish Museum of Modern Art, Heritage Ireland, and Johnstown Castle in addition to Irish universities. However, this distribution is not new as it mirrors the geographic and institutional skewing in attendance at the 2023 and 2024 Annual Events (2025 breakdown to be determined). **The Association has a growth opportunity in expansion to support more Irish and GLAM colleagues.** Subsequent recommendations will seek to address this, however they may be limited by the lack of respondent input.

The perception of what qualifies as DH work is in flux for respondents. 35 respondents (70%) consider the work they do DH, while 14 (28%) sometimes consider their work as DH. However, the perspectives of respondents' institutional homes did not consistently align with their views of their own work. 4 respondents who see their work as DH (3 of whom were at GLAM institutions) say that their institutions only sometimes agree. Yet 3 respondents working at HEIs who saw their work as only sometimes DH described their institutions as always considering their work under the umbrella of DH. While the discrepancy is small, it seems that **HEIs may disproportionately highlight work as digital humanities while GLAM institutions resist similar labels.**

Terminology of Digital Humanities

The DH community is full of widely skilled practitioners and the terminology is in flux. Survey respondents offered a wide range of qualitative answers when asked if they found the label of Digital Humanities useful (Question 10). Several found it convenient ('Convenient, well understood', 'Yes it pays the bills', 'it's my job title

and the name of [my] institution'). Many felt that it was mainly useful for communicating with folks that already knew or identified with the label ('flexible [...] and is widely understood', 'Yes, though it's hard to get anyone not already identifying as within that field to be interested', 'A catch all phrase that [people] understand', 'Useful for forming community, difficult to explain to people "outside" though'). Others found the label of 'digital' ill-fitting, and thought alternative frameworks might be more appropriate ('I think the "digital" bit needs updating. Everything is "digital" now.', 'To me is not particularly useful, but to some of my colleagues it is as [it] allows [them] to [make] explicit more easily their degree of involvement with "the digital"'). Several did not find the designation useful at all, suggesting that it was either too general ('I find it too broad.', 'No. the definition is too broad.', 'In some contexts it can be helpful [...] in other situations it is too broad a category') or inadequately confusing ('Not really, it confuses people but also seems reductive', 'I don't think it communicates well, either to "outsiders" or to students, who are often anxious about whether their proposed work is actually DH."

Several respondents felt that using digital humanities to refer to methodology rather than discipline was the most interesting way forward. One respondent used it 'mostly to describe my methodologically-driven research.' Another described their research hubs avoiding the label while also finding it 'useful for theoretical/methodological discussions'. Another suggested that they historically associated it with methods rather than "digital culture" which led to disconnect in their practice. The personal nature of respondents' relationship with the term was effectively captured by one mid-career academic, who '[thinks] of DH as a methodological approach rather than a discipline. Akin to computational social science. If that's how it's being used, [then it is] useful. But most people don't use it that way.' There is a sense that respondents are making their own meaning in and through the terminology of digital humanities ('some people see it as a bit passe now, and others have no idea what it means').

There is room for the Association to leverage its authority to help clarify what 'DH' can and does mean in the region while incorporating more specific terminology into their community building and advocacy. Other terms suggested by respondents as useful included 'Digital Research', 'Cultural

Analytics', or 'Digital Textual Studies'. One suggested that they found 'Digital Scholarship' to be a more inclusive label; in conversation, Professor Jane Winters agreed, indicating that 'Digital Scholarship feels more inclusive than Digital Humanities, but DH has a brand.' This could have resonance with other respondents' perceived animosity from other disciplines ('negative connotations for humanities people who regard it as inferior to "real" humanities').

Organizational Membership

More than half of respondents indicated that they are a member of at least one association to support their professional needs (Question 22: 24/44 respondents; 54.54%). 19 respondents (43.18%) suggested that they are not members of DH associations, and one British practitioner indicated that they were technically involved in their institution's internal DH network, but that it had mostly 'fizzled out.'

Of those in associations, suggestions on potential improvements highlighted overwhelm (Question 23). DH is a broad discipline, so many respondents found that they felt less useful or that lots of active engagement was required to establish usefulness. Some said that it was 'not always clear what they do' or needed to 'be more public facing'. Advocacy, or the perception of it, seemed a gap, as one late-career British HEI respondent indicated their dissatisfaction that associations 'want money but I don't [see] them doing much advocating for DH.'

Transparency and tangible benefits would benefit the Association going forward.

Of those not currently in an association, the reasoning varied. Some suggested that they did not know what benefits would be provided or whom to associate with since they felt tangentially affiliated with DH. Others highlighted the potential benefits in terms of community building and bringing folks together, yet had not found the time or resources to concretise that association for their own practice. One Mid-career DH practitioner suggested that they found associations mostly inaccessible for neurodivergent people; another critiqued the way that the idea of 'community' is tied into attending a conference. While physical access and regional isolation was not highlighted as an issue, **offering a**

diversity of modalities for networking and engagement to support neurodiversity may help the Association grow.

Fewer respondents participate in advocacy or networking groups, but if they did, they went all in (Question 24). 14/43 respondents indicated that they are involved in multiple advocacy or networking groups (32.56%) while 2 (4.65%) were involved in only one group. Those involved in these groups were at a range of career stages, but no students were involved. Group participants sought more visibility from their advocacy and networking groups around public outreach and systemic change (Question 25). 9 participants (20.93%) suggested that they would like to be a part of an advocacy group, but were not aware of any that would represent their interest. Once again, **clarity and transparency seem critical for members to identify the value of their participation in community-oriented professional organizations.**

Experience and Methodologies

Respondents were asked about their skills and experiences as related to the professionalization of DH as a field (Question 11). The multiple choice options provided were pulled from DH job postings at the time of the ethics application; additionally, there was an 'other' option so that respondents could include unlisted experiences. 5 respondents (10%) abstained from answering the question.

DH is a multidisciplinary community and no respondent listed one isolated expertise. The most popular domain expertise was 'data and information literacy', with 30 respondents (66.67%) indicating experience. This was followed by 'coding' (27 respondents, 60%), 'digital archiving' (24 respondents; 53.33%) and 'AI applications in the humanities' (24 respondents; 53.33%). The least common expertises were 'multimedia digital art' (4 respondents; 8.89%), 'algorithmic justice' (7 respondents; 15.56%), and 'media infrastructures' (9 respondents; 20%).

These answers can be paired with responses to a later question about how the Association can best support respondents (Question 26), which suggested that 31/44 respondees (70.45%) would want training opportunities promoted and

21/44 respondees (47.73%) would want the association to host short courses on relevant skill acquisition, thus also providing teaching opportunities. **The Association can provide requested value through opportunities to knowledge share and upskill around the expertises requested by jobs in the field.**

Connection

Respondents use a range of methods to find out about new opportunities (Question 13). Email lists such as the Association's are very popular, alongside jobs.ac.uk, [ArtsJobs](https://www.artsjobs.com), [Humanist](https://www.humanist.org.uk), [AoIR](https://www.aolr.com), and department lists. Yet respondents identified several weaknesses in the mailing list approach (Question 14), including the limitations of the filtering systems and the constant vigilance required to keep on top of everything; one respondent categorised the process as 'exhausting'.

Relationship building and networking is also very popular with 'word of mouth' and 'pro-active relationship building' or 'recommendations from my network' common answers. Overall, it seems that **the Association's mailing list provides a lot of value and should be maintained.**

Yet even though DH as a field is growing, many opportunities are only available to those who are already connected. Systemic knowledge seemed a big barrier, as jobseekers need to 'know about those [mailing] lists' or know that 'job roles are advertised within arts and heritage website portals' and that mailing lists are 'often based on the network you're in'.

Word of mouth works, and helps those already embedded into the community. One respondent said that the system was 'very effective in keeping [them] in work; it's fundamentally unfair, since not everyone has access to the same networks.' Another suggested that they only found out about their current role via 'word of mouth close to the deadline'. An Irish DH practitioner indicated that they found DH to be 'quite a cliquy space' and that 'buddy groups determine most collabs' (Question 21).

In terms of better integrating newer DH professionals into existing opportunity networks, 30/44 respondents (68.18%) suggested that the Association could provide value by hosting networking events. 27/44 respondents (61.36%) suggested that the Association could provide small grants to encourage inter-institutional collaborations, which may benefit those less formally embedded into DH roles.

Social media can help widen access to posts and is a popular option for finding out about collaborations and opportunities. When asked which social media platforms respondents used (Question 15), the majority suggested LinkedIn (33/45 respondents; 73.33%). Other platforms that respondents engaged with included Bluesky (21/45; 46.67%), Facebook (12/45; 26.67%) and Instagram (10/45 respondents wrote in; 22.22%). While X, formerly known as Twitter, used to be quite popular among academics and GLAM professionals, only 4 of the respondents (8.89%) indicated that they use it now. Depending on the amount of resources the Association would like to dedicate to social media and promotion, **they can establish a more regular presence on LinkedIn as a priority**, followed by Bluesky and Facebook; multimodal engagement seems best to reach a broader range of interested DH practitioners.

Collaboration

Highlighting and expanding collaborative projects is a good opportunity for the Association to provide value. The vast majority of survey respondents indicated that they collaborated regularly as part of their role (Question 16). Most were open to collaborating with external partners at GLAM institutions or HEIs (Question 17: 44/45 respondents; 97.78%) and indicated that they were interested in engaging in more collaborative projects (Question 20: 41/45; 91.11%). Two of the four respondents who were not interested in more collaboration cited lack of available time as the reason, with one suggesting that they try to redirect potential collaborations to other colleagues.

Respondents seek a range of attributes in potential collaborators, most of which are unsurprising (Question 18). Curiosity and willingness to learn, humility, open mindedness, flexibility, and enthusiasm were common answers. Many respondents sought collaborators with complementary skillsets, yet a

non-antagonistic disciplinary grounding. Good attitude was also highlighted as desirable ('someone we enjoy working with!', 'Someone I'd want to work with on a personal level.', 'Willingness to treat others as equal partners') while ego was criticised ('Not being an arse.')

Unreliability, either due to lack of interest or overwhelm, was a frustration ('ability to reply to email', 'can meet internal deadlines', 'willing/able to deliver to a set of agreed and shared goals', 'I can trust them to deliver'). One response from a late-career GLAM professional on what they look for in a collaborator is worth including in its entirety:

Sanity - a realistic expectation of what my GLAM can deliver. Respect for non-academic partners, which includes reasonable reimbursement and recognition for our roles in a project. That the potential collaborators are willing to listen and might be nice people to work with

Divergent expectations don't only occur between disciplines, but also in institutional possibilities. It is interesting that 'respect' is framed not just as an interpersonal attitude, but also as an infrastructural norm, through bureaucracies like 'reasonable reimbursement'. **The Association could improve collaborative possibilities by facilitating conversations and offering best practice guidance around inter-institutional collaborations and needs.**

The most popular collaboration tools (Question 19) were Github and Google Drive/Docs (9 respondents each), followed by Trello (8 respondents) and Zoom or Teams (7 respondents). Slack, Miro, and Discord were also featured. A few highlighted institutional restrictions on what tools they were permitted to use and suggested that complex tools can be 'more hassle than they're often worth'. There were a range of responses to this challenge; some developed 'bespoke platforms' for their data while others found that 'humanities researchers dislike using IT systems beyond email, Facebook, or Teams.' The technical openness and adaptability of collaborators seems to be a potential obstacle that the Association could address, either by **providing collaborative tool trainings** or redirecting members to existing resources.

Next Steps

To best understand how the Association can support affiliates and potential future members, we asked them (Question 26). While I have alluded to a few of the respondent's recommendations in previous sections based on domain relevance, it may be useful to cluster them around popularity; especially in this period of rapid growth, the Association will prioritise the most requested advocacy efforts and resource allocations.

44 respondents answered the question and the most popular support methods for the Association to undertake were **promotion of training opportunities** and **advocating for the value of DH research and teaching** (31 respondents each; 70.45%). While many respondents requested both, these recommendations do not represent a unified subset of respondents and highlight the internal-external duality of advocacy for the DH community. The Association needs to simultaneously support growth of the community from within while defending it from external pressures. These tied in, respectively, with recommendations to **host short courses on relevant skill acquisition** (21 respondents; 47.73%) and **publish case studies to highlight non-traditional career paths** (23 respondents; 52.27%). While the Association could offer a forum to publish work, which was moderately popular among respondents (19 respondents; 43.18%), subsequent recommendations from the workshop rejected this suggestion.

The Association has an opportunity to facilitate new connections, socially and/or financially. Two popular suggestions were for the Association to **host networking events** (30 respondents; 68.18%) and **provide small grants to encourage inter-institutional collaboration** (27 respondents; 61.36%). While respondents previously highlighted some of the difficulties and seeming pre-determination of collaborative projects,

Additional write-in suggestions from respondents included offering not just collaborative grants, but individual funding (e.g. for training, research dissemination). Another suggestion was to offer pedagogical knowledge exchange opportunities since 'everyone teaches DH differently, and we could have a lot to learn from each other', which could be folded into networking events.

The least successful options were to provide certification for skills relevant to future employment (7 respondents; 15.91%) and to offer training in positioning skillsets to pivot into a new industry (6 respondents; 13.64%). I interpret this as profoundly optimistic; even though there are challenges facing DH, folks want to stick around and expand the community rather than leave it.

Question 27 shifted the focus from the individual respondents themselves to their recommendations for the Association to grow the community as a whole. The most popular suggestion, that the Association **directly lobby with government organizations for funding and visibility** (27/41 respondents; 65.85%) echoed the advocacy recommendation from Question 26. Government organizations were not the only target, as 23 respondents (56.1%) suggested **public-facing interest group coalitions be established** around more specialized domain expertises.

Many respondents, albeit not quite a majority, suggested that the Association **facilitate training around community organizing** (19 respondents; 46.34%). It seems that folks are willing to be involved in community building to a point, but hope that the Association will step in to provide the big picture focus.

Overall, respondents seem interested in the Association establishing itself as a defining and communicative body externally, which can articulate value and facilitate community building internally.

The Workshop

The Advocacy workshop was held on 17 June during the Association's Annual Event at the University of Glasgow. Attendees were few (two participants) but they were enthusiastic and knowledgeable. One participant was the head of a DH department at a Russell Group university while the other worked in outreach at the [Arts and Humanities Research Council](#) (AHRC), which provides UK-based funding for arts and humanities research. They represented great expertise in the field and offered generous suggestions from both the grant writing and grant approval sides of DH.

Community collaboration and communication were noted as areas for growth. While the participants are at mature stages of their careers, they both noted that the workflow for collaboration trends towards asking friends they have already worked with previously. Redirection and expansion is needed, especially towards working more internationally and interdisciplinarily. One suggested path out was to share opportunities in a casual platform like Slack, rather than via a more centralised mailing list.

The Association's relationship with **existing DH Organizations** and publications was discussed in depth. Participants suggested not joining an umbrella organization, such as the Alliance of Digital Humanities Organizations (ADHO), or starting another journal as an avenue for advocacy.

Funding was highlighted as a key challenge that is only becoming more dire. AHRC's role as a funder and broker was discussed as well as the changing funding mechanisms and priorities of AHRC/UKRI following the government/spending review. The British Council was identified as a potential avenue since they have many types of funding applications and can support training and capacity building without costing the Association personnel time.

I invoked **radical advocacy models** from queer theory, disability studies, and prison abolition in order to expand possible thinking and imagine futures of solidarity. This prompted participants to consider how we might escape a scarcity mindset to reach a more generous community; there was a feeling that right now, collaboration feels like admitting to having a weakness. Another idea was to offer grant application review opportunities and post-mortems. However, the participants noted that this kind of trust takes time to build, both in the Association and with each other. Without a full-time community manager like the Software Sustainability Institute's or the AHRC's, this sort of community sharing will need to be collaborative. When asked to dream up what the Association should do if given astronomical resources, participants recommended growing the community through funded PhD studentships.

The Interviews

While the survey was anonymous, respondents were given the opportunity to provide their email addresses to be contacted for attributed interviews (Questions 29 and 30). Additionally, I reached out to the Software Sustainability Institute (SSI) and the Royal Historical Society (RHS) to gain insight from their related advocacy models.

Kristen Schuster, Lecturer in Digital Humanities

University of Southampton

Dr Kristen Schuster is a lecturer in [Digital Humanities at the University of Southampton](#). The Department was founded in 2021 and hosts a Digital Humanities (Data Science) MSc in addition to collaborating with GLAM institutions by supporting [Digital Preservation Southampton](#).

Dr Schuster's research focuses on information management and data ontologies and they lead current projects on queering LLM chatbots. They have also been involved in organizing and supporting the Association over the past few years. They described the existing ways that the Association helps support members, such as through flexible stipends and bursaries for the Annual Event. 'The only kind of caveat is that you do have to come to the annual event, but if you need it for plane tickets, if you need it for hotels, if you need it for like childcare [...] it's money that is meant to make your life easier.' But Dr Schuster describes how it is challenging to scale the community before the corresponding resources, 'it is really nice being able to offer stipends and bursaries for the annual event. But you know, and legitimately the feedback that we do get, get from participants is I wish it had been more. [...] it would be so nice if we could have more of the bursaries and at a kind of larger sum.' In this instance, more is more, and larger bursaries will hopefully be possible as the Association scales.

Dr Schuster draws a lot of inspiration in their work with the Association from the DH research and community at Southampton. There, they run a successful series of workshops open to all at the University which cover pieces of software or digital methods. They also coordinate a student internship programme modeled

on professional work experience which prioritises both research and expectation setting. A large part of the structure involves '[making] sure that this is a good example for how you should be treated in academia and the workplace.' These sorts of teaching and learning opportunities are very valuable and could be incorporated into the Association's events strategy going forward, but Dr Schuster recognizes that what works at Southampton can't serve every need for the Association. Their goal for the Association's teaching and learning is variety:

I think one thing with training is that having a range of different interesting kinds of ideas, right, and and topics, kind of having them scaffolded to introductory, intermediate, and advanced [...] but having those kinds of clearly signposted sets of skills. And then, you know, sometimes self-paced, sometimes online, sometimes in person, I think would be really great. [...] And not just also focusing on technical things, but saying, how do you fill in an AHRC budget?

By incorporating both technical research skills and organizational skills or social experience, multifaceted trainings can more fully support Association members.

Dr Schuster, along with several of the subsequent interviewees, highlighted that a big part of training and collaborative communication can feel like you are expressing weakness or exposing yourself to vulnerability:

And I think building the confidence in yourself as a researcher to not feel challenged or threatened when somebody asks for that clarity so that you actually view it as an opportunity for conversation is really important. But then also having the kind of soft skill set to know how and when to ask other researchers for that clarification. Because it can come off as a kind of like power play, right?

This sort of confidence comes with time and experience in supportive collaborations, but if the Association can work to reduce stigma around this type of communication and growth, the community may benefit.

Mark Hill, Lecturer in Cultural Computation

King's College London

Dr Mark J. Hill is a lecturer in Cultural Computation in the [Department of Digital Humanities at KCL](#). The Centre for Computing in the Humanities at KCL was

founded in 1992 and later converted to become the DH department, making it a pioneering institution in the UK.

Dr Hill focuses on intellectual history and computational social sciences and has experience researching in the Nordic and Baltic DH communities. He sees 'DH less as a discipline and more as a broad set of methodologies'. As such, he is 'a big fan of international collaboration', especially in post-Brexit UK. Whether collaborators align around methodology or area of interest, they can offer fruitful resonances that expands research possibilities.

He views events, training, and conferences as the first step towards community and meaningful collaboration: 'from a personal pragmatic perspective, [we need] opportunities to meet potential collaborators or just people who you have opportunities to communicate with and discuss ideas with'. However, Dr Hill identified the risk with interdisciplinary events and networking in DH is that the lack of concrete definition around what the discipline is can lead to 'vague' and 'general themes that conferences build themselves around.' If events can instead provide a 'much more technical, methods focus, [...] practical engagements in all different disciplines of the humanities' then more meaningful collaborative opportunities will arise.

I asked Dr Hill about the tensions or slippages in terminology use between computational and humanities researchers. He found language to be a common point of disconnect between domains and highlighted how terms can mean different things to different types of researchers. But he finds that research style can be a more systemic communications issue, with computer scientists operationalizing work in a more linear way, while humanists undertake a 'much more exploratory, iterative approach and might actually not know how to frame questions to make them answerable by computer scientists.' Thus, supporting the development of shared terminology, either via a community encyclopedia like [The Living Glossary of Digital Narrative](#), or through collaborative practice guidance, could be an opportunity for the Association to provide value.

Dr Hill also discussed training opportunities, which he is a big proponent of. He is 'really happy to try to upskill if [he] can' and signs up based on how interesting

the topic sounds. But he acknowledges the risk and the difficulty in finding the right place or the right time to train:

It's not really possible to learn how to do these things unless you're applying them to a thing which you know about or have interest in. So until it was project based and a project that I was interested in, I wasn't able to really retain any information. [...] I think, especially as you move further along in a career, there's a level of vulnerability to saying, I still need training, I still need upskilling. It can feel slightly threatening to admit that you don't know something.

The Association can potentially provide value by integrating trainings with potential projects or collaborations, whether this is by offering method-based hackathons or providing project-oriented networking events like the [SSI's Collaborations Workshops](#).

We discussed the common trend of signing up for events and then choosing not to attend on the day due to lack of time. He suggested that in-person events, with the logistical concerns that come with it, are 'much easier to slice out that time and put it in your calendar'. He finds himself more able to engage rather than trying to answer emails while attending virtually. However, he acknowledged that his base in London provides an abundance of in-person events and that online offerings can be useful too.

In terms of finding out about events, he primarily leverages mailing lists, which he siphons into their own inbox folder so that they don't pose a persistent distraction. He highlighted the Association's mailing list as a useful structure, in addition to the [Turing Institute's digital culture mailing list](#) and the [ARtificial Intelligence for Environment & Sustainability \(ARIES\)](#) list.

Andy Corrigan, Digital Library Coordinator

University of Cambridge Libraries and Archives

The [University of Cambridge Libraries and Archives](#) are a collection of departmental and archival libraries and collections in the University of

Cambridge. The central University Library is a legal deposit repository, and as such houses new British and Irish publications either in print or digital form. The [Cambridge Digital Library](#) was launched in 2011 and is a platform for digitised material and related research outputs from the University of Cambridge and beyond. The team collaborates with other institutions, such as the [Bodleian Library at Oxford](#), and researchers to both expand scholarship on digital materials and share knowledge around digital preservation best practices. The Digital Library team members are also affiliated with [Cambridge Digital Humanities](#), a research group that hosts an MPhil in Digital Humanities.

Andy Corrigan is the Digital Library Coordinator at Cambridge and finds that his role provides a lot of flexibility since he works at the intersection of academic DH research and library work. He collaborates extensively, but not systematically, which he finds to be a strength. 'I think the way the DH community in the UK seems to operate is that I think it's fairly reliant on humans and on people's relationships with each other.' Mr Corrigan finds the connections and collaborations 'more to do with people [...] than the institutions.' This helps researchers connect across disciplinary bounds, but relies on pre-existing networks which can be a challenge to newer or less connected practitioners. 'We rely on word of mouth quite a lot. We find it can be easier or more fruitful [...] to collaborate with other institutions and projects [...] The bureaucracy of somewhere like Cambridge can be a barrier, so we really value anything that helps facilitate those conversations.'

To stay connected, Mr Corrigan is a member of [Research Libraries UK](#) and the [Association of European Research Libraries](#) (LIBER) where he participates in their digital scholarship and culture working group, which he finds especially helpful in facilitating European collaborations post-Brexit. But he finds his roles as both a librarian and a DH researcher at odds, '[I'm] trying to decide whether I should put all my money on joining library associations or whether I should be joining DH associations. [...] I've kind of been asking myself that question for years and never really got on a concrete spot [...] I think in retrospect maybe that's a strength in a way because that does allow me [...] flexibility.' The Association has a strength in explicitly trying to bridge the divide between GLAM and HEI research, but this is unlikely to occur organically and will require concerted

effort. Overwhelm and oversaturation are a problem, 'There's lots of other communities that I know it would be good to engage with [like [AI4LAM](#)]. It's just like these days there seems to be so many that finding the time to do everything is just impossible.'

Mr Corrigan appreciates more localized organizations like the Association because he finds them more accessible. He explained that global DH associations can be a bit unwieldy and difficult to navigate if you don't already know how they work; they are big and complicated and may have useful interesting research, but it's in an inaccessible place. 'we don't have a huge amount of funding for paying for travel or anything. [...] Zoom and things help but it's not quite the same as being able to just sit somewhere and say "Okay, Can we have a coffee and figure this out?"'

He finds that the Association facilitates community that is easier to access and sustain:

'What I like about what the [UK-Ireland Association] have been doing over the last couple of years is making it more of an entrance point. [...] you can come to a UK Ireland DH event now and you can kind of feel like you get what's going on a little bit. [...] Actually what's meaningful is that kind of community of interaction and being able to participate.'

While this type of community ease may become more challenging as the Association scales, if accessibility can remain a priority then it should still facilitate meaningful collaboration and community.

Valentina Vavassori, Digital Curator for Automatic Text Recognition

The British Library

The British Library as an information infrastructure embodies many of the possibilities and challenges of the digital humanities in the cultural heritage sector on a very public stage. In June-October 2023, the BL hosted a [Digital Storytelling exhibition](#) which showcased born digital interactive and multimedia

stories. But at the end of October 2023, the British Library experienced a [malicious cyber-attack](#) which took out many systems and services. While the entire library suffered, the digital collections were particularly impacted.

Extensive work has gone into restoring access to these resources, and now over [2,000 digitised manuscripts](#) are available. Online journal articles and E-books are [scheduled to be restored in 2026](#), but there is no timeline for restoration of born-digital content, video and moving image content, or the National Radio Archive materials, among others.

Dr Valentina Vavassori is a Digital Curator at [The British Library](#) (BL), the national library of the UK. She is responsible for Automatic Text Recognition (OCR and HTR) within the Heritage Made Digital team which brings digitised heritage collections to new audiences. She works in all languages across the library and engages with every stage of work, from research projects to operational pipelines. She is involved with [AI for Libraries, Archives and Museums](#) (AI4LAM) and has joined the Association to try and see more opportunities available to folks from the creative industries or cultural heritage, not just academics. She describes how her interests in international copyright and high performance computing could have many resonances with those in research domains: 'it would be nice to have a kind of hub just saying, if you're interested, just speak with this person or that one.'

While Dr Vavassori was affiliated with an HEI during her PhD, she found the transition into GLAM very smooth as she still works with many of the same people and attends the same events, but recognizes that this shift was largely due to her exceptional project-based background:

During my PhD, I had the opportunity to work a lot as a research assistant, so I was involved in a lot of projects. I got a lot of skill out of that which gave me the ability then to progress [...] when I started doing the interviews for roles, they want something practical. And academic wise, unless you are someone who goes and learns how to do things, [...] there was nobody there that offered that kind of training for skills. [...] I learned to code myself and just after years I managed to get a course on Python

Providing short trainings, and thus also teaching opportunities could be a good way for the Association to offer value to members. This could support career pivots and better cross-pollination between HEIs and GLAM organizations.

Yet domain pivots and interdisciplinary collaboration create frictions around language, as discussed with Dr Hill. But Dr Vavassori approaches communication with an openness that helps sustain collaboration 'Sometimes [collaborators] don't have the same concept, but I mean, they are open to learn. I am open to explain. If we use different words, let's clarify to each other. It's not always possible, but you can try.'

This style of communication can extend to pedagogy too. Dr Vavassori described a collaboration with the Javanese community in Bali, where she did a workshop on Wikisource and machine learning. 'At the end of the two hours of workshop, I ended up learning much more from them than they probably learned from me, but they were really happy.' By sustaining openness in her pedagogy, Dr Vavassori is able to grow and expand through her teachings and collaboration. If the Association could support a generous style of clarifying communication, either through trainings or example, that could provide value and improve the viability of collaboration.

Neil Chue Hong, Director of the Software Sustainability Institute

The [Software Sustainability Institute](#) (SSI) supports the development of 'better and more sustainable software to enable world-class research.' It was started in 2010 and is led by the [University of Edinburgh](#) in partnership with the [University of Manchester](#) and the [University of Southampton](#). They offer a variety of resources to individual researchers, such as [intermediate software skills courses](#), advocacy organizations, like their [Event Organisation Guide](#), and funders, such as their range of [research impact reports](#).

As an international organization with fantastic track records in advocacy and research, I was keen to learn from their practice to inform the Association's own efforts. Prof Neil Chue Hong, director of the SSI, was kind enough to speak with me about the history of SSI and how it works. He is a researcher-practitioner, as his own research interests are around software sustainability and community engagement, which he also undertakes through SSI.

SSI hosts several programmes and initiatives to support research, including their annual [Collaborations Workshops](#), which function as a sort of un-conference and are driven by an interest in finding and sustaining active research collaboration. They also run an annual Fellowship programme, which includes a stipend, networking opportunities, and mentorship; this supports community building and development of future advocates, and former-fellows are still valued as practitioners and community-members long after their term has concluded.

The Collaborations Workshops are particularly important to the ethos and success of SSI, as it demonstrates the ways that the institution prioritises growth and exchange in its community rather than immediate output. Prof Chue Hong explained that the workshops actually pre-date the SSI, and were originally more traditional conferences, but were restructured to look more like Foo Camps or hackathons: 'the thing that we had seen in the early days of the Collaborations Workshop was that people were really enthusiastic but then when they went back, no one had any time. So we introduced an optional third day, to give people a chance to realise some of the ideas they had developed in the workshop.' Now, the events start with participant lightning talks to present research interests and questions, and move swiftly into conversation as the centrepiece, rather than the bit that happens in the hallways between panels. SSI has tried gamifying the workshop a bit, to make it more fun, 'We do incentivise it quite a lot because we tend to run it as a sort of light competition. There are little prizes for each stage for the best ideas, best kind of prototypes and so on.' While there is no need for the Association to replicate SSI's work in this area, establishing pathways for more collaborative-focused events would strengthen the network of members and align with the requests from the survey for greater collaborative opportunities.

Prof Chue Hong also highlighted the fellowship programme as a key value to the SSI community and one that the Association could adopt, 'A lot of the success of what we do has been around how we run [the Fellowship] program and how we get people talking to each other. Because these are all people from across the disciplinary areas.' Fellows collaborate or expand on their work through interdisciplinary pressure by joining a supportive research community. Additionally, since SSI has such interdisciplinary appeal, Fellows gain concrete opportunities through their association, 'for instance, if we see that someone's looking for a speaker, or someone who could be on an organizing or advisory committee, we can kind of go, "we think this person might be good to take a look at" so that we're just kind of knitting a fabric of all of these great people around the place.' Considering how oriented the DH landscape and opportunities in UK and Ireland seem to be around word of mouth and personal connections, this sort of facilitation is invaluable and would be a great advocacy effort for the Association. Prof Chue Hong explained that some earlier Fellows are now running their own DH departments or have C-suite roles in industry, so the system has been successful in helping folks network and expand their research.

SSI is exemplary in the way it breeds spin off organizations that grow out of its fellowships, collaborations, or research. For instance, they initially established the language around research software engineering (RSE), which now has a great community and practice. They try to work as a community and discipline connector, but Prof Chue Hong sees their role as evolving, 'Mostly what we were doing was trying to create communities of practice in areas that were more interdisciplinary but still quite focused. So in the early days, we were doing work with communities like biofilms which involve biology, physics and chemistry, all closely related disciplines [...] Now we tend to be working more with larger interdisciplinary more international groups focusing on cross-cutting challenges.'

While SSI has a longstanding durability, Prof Chue Hong still sees the organization as one that evolves through each round of funding and adapts as the landscape shifts:

'In an ideal world, what we're trying to do is get funding to set up an area so that other people can come in. And then we move out of that area and go forward and do the next bit. So we're breaking new

ground, but we're not necessarily the people that are going to be [...] farming it long term. It's an interesting kind of methodology, because it really scares my team. We have to shift and adapt.'

It's useful to remember that no matter how well established or well funded an organization, evolution is still risky. Visionary teams do not form by accident; it's an uncomfortable process. If the Association can maintain flexibility and treat this sort of commitment to growing the DH landscape as essential rather than aspirational or a goal for the future, then we will be able to support more meaningful collaborations.

In terms of scaling advocacy and best practices, Prof Chue Hong recommended resources from the [Center for Scientific Collaboration and Community Engagement](#) (CSCCE), whose founder used to be UK-based but now has a more North American and international focus; the center offers trainings and certifications around community engagement leadership.

Philip Carter, Director of the Royal Historical Society

The [Royal Historical Society](#) was recommended by interviewees and workshop attendees multiple times as an organization that performs really strong advocacy works and provides sustained value to its members. Founded in 1868, the RHS has over 7000 members, mainly in the UK but also internationally. The Society's stated goals, as listed [on their website](#), are that the Society:

- ADVOCATES for historians and the value of history
- BUILDS connections between historians of all kinds
- CELEBRATES the diversity of our historical communities
- CHAMPIONS environments in which history may flourish
- FACILITATES historical enquiry through funding and publishing

They offer small grant funding, research prizes, and publish the journal *Transactions* in addition to several series of scholarly editions and new publications. In terms of advocacy, they publish public statements in support of historians and at-risk departments. They collaborate with other historical societies to publish statements and advocacy briefings. Since 2023, members of the Society's Council have engaged directly with British MPs to advocate for

support of the discipline. Of particular note is the Society's [2024 report](#) on 'The Value of History in UK Higher Education and Society'.

I spoke with Dr Philip Carter, Director of the Royal Historical Society, who leads the advocacy initiatives of the Society. He noted that 'advocacy is a catch-all phrase' that can mean many things. For the Royal Historical Society, they divide their advocacy work into three streams, 'one of which is this response to need, which is the demand that people have to promote and defend their work [...] Second, I suppose there's a public dimension too, and this is becoming more prominent in recent months [...] to try and shape the debate around the value of history' and third is 'helping the membership at this time [of change].'

1. Respond to Need

Dr Carter explained that a lot of the RHS's advocacy work is conducted behind the scenes, confidential work, around limiting departmental cuts and highlighting the potential damages. Dr Carter highlighted that one of the challenges of advocacy is that in many instances 'we will never know whether we've been successful or not.' But through public statements and confidential support, members feel heard. The RHS, too, is working to build connections following a membership survey of their own; Dr Carter explained that:

providing connections between people is really important. A lot of people at the moment feel isolated [...] much more scattered [...] people feel like they're losing their contact and identity and it's subject based organizations' job to step in and provide that mentorship and that connection.

While DH, as an interdisciplinary community, faces different challenges around identity loss and fragmentation, the structure of an organization providing cohering support feels applicable.

Another way that the RHS supports community is through their events. Since before COVID, they held annual department visits which were affiliated with an invited public lecture, funded by the RHS. Now, this structure works to bring historians in different departments and across an organization together; 'it's actually very very hard often to find everybody [...] so it's a way of bringing people together and celebrating what they do.' The events also bring together

the broader community. The public and institutional administrators come out to see the good work that internal historians are doing and the RHS highlights their importance in the discipline.

2. Public Outreach

The RHS has recently started engaging directly with the British Parliament around advocating for the value of history. Dr Carter explained that it was easier than they expected to contact and engage with MPs who were interested in history, but that it is difficult to translate speaking with individual MPs towards outcomes. He found that individual MPs 'were interested, but following through is very difficult because the individual MP has no purchase [...] so one of the challenges if you want to work in Parliament [...] is to think about how you might aggregate MPs.' He recommended trying to engage on an organizational level with pre-existing networks to develop more traction.

One specific opportunity he highlights were the select committees, which occasionally ask for data or input surrounding investigations, which are infrequent asks which can help establish the Association as an expert in the domain. One such opportunity currently available is through the British Parliament's Education Committee, which has an inquiry open to evidence around [the use of Artificial Intelligence and EdTech in Education](#). The Irish Oireachtas Committee on Enterprise, Tourism and Employment have similar public consultation structures, and currently are open to submissions around [Regulation of Artificial Intelligence in Ireland](#).

3. Adapting to Change

Funding and governmental support has changed in recent years and even mature organizations like the RHS may not be able to prevent that change. However, there is a difference between accepting change and adapting to it. Dr Carter described how the RHS has adjusted its funding structure:

We cannot stop the transition, but we can try and make it as painless as we can to limit the damage [...] that means things like restructuring how we give out grant money, appreciating that a lot of organizations that used to give out £1000 or £2000 for research don't do that

anymore [...] [we are] stepping up and stepping into the breach where there are gaps emerging.

It is difficult to see how to apply this sense of awareness to the advocacy efforts of less endowed organizations like the Association, but perhaps filling new gaps in pre-existing support structures can be a good first step towards providing concrete community value.

However, while many things are changing simultaneously, it is difficult to focus. Dr Carter highlighted the difference between advocacy and campaigning around their intentionality. While advocacy is a process which offers general engagement and outreach, a campaign can provide clarity: 'campaigning is quite useful because it gives you a focus and you can say this year, this six months, we're doing this, this is our message.' That clarity can help drive impact and hopefully achieve concrete progress towards targeted advocacy aims. A campaign-based advocacy model seems like it could be beneficial for the Association.

Conclusions and Recommendations

There are lots of recommendations that could be beneficial to the growth and expansion of the Association's membership. As highlighted by Dr Carter, it is difficult to know what success might look like. However, heeding the insights from the Association's community and mature organizations is a great step in the right direction.

I have divided the recommendations and requests into three application categories: connection through events, support through collaboration, and growth through publications. The intention here is that the collective feels equipped to prioritise whichever recommendations or actions they feel will be most beneficial.

Community Connection Through Events

The Association hosts an Annual Event to bring together the DH community of UK and Ireland. The Event has been held throughout the region, in London (2023), Cork (2024), Glasgow (2025), and Southampton (2026). While these events

are well attended, an additional programme could be beneficial, including virtual and regional networking events. In particular, events targeted around (1) teaching and sharing pedagogical tools and (2) communication and knowledge sharing between GLAM and HEI practitioners seem to be gaps in the landscape that the Association could fill. Events targeted for Irish and GLAM members should be prioritised, or at least given equal attention.

Not all events, however, are equal in terms of organizational or implementation effort; an online happy hour is much easier to set up than a python workshop. The Annual Event should remain the priority, but additional events that may be relatively straightforward to trial:

- **Existing events** - encourage members to share events through the mailing list to help connect community members.
- **Engage existing event infrastructure** - Reach out to DH-related event and workshop coordinators, such as [Wikimedia UK](#), to host dedicated events like a [Wikipedia edit-a-thon](#). Alternatively, help interested members connect to 'attend' asynchronous virtual trainings as 'classmates', such as the [SSI's training resources](#).
- **Local meetups** - identify local coordinators through applications or direct outreach and help spread the word about a social event. Provide a small stipend to support a 'round' for attendees at a cafe or bar.
- **Dedicated Seminars** - host webinars or conversations around pedagogical skills, community organizing, or collaborative tool trainings.

Hopefully the Association team and community can determine the ideal calendar balance in terms of organizational effort and impact, but this is likely to vary based on location and interest. Trial and error may ultimately prove to be the best practice method for programming events.

Community Support Through Collaboration

Social Media

The Association could benefit from an expanded social media presence, particularly on LinkedIn (as indicated by responses to Question 15 in the survey).

If the Association could run a [page](#), it could provide relatively straightforward connection:

- Demonstrate the breadth of the Association's membership community and help reach potential members
- Amplify members' 'wins' and achievements by sharing their posts
- Improve visibility for Association events and other Advocacy efforts

Fellowship Programme

A more extensive fellowship programme, [modeled after SSI's](#), could provide an array of benefits if the Association could secure financial support. In helping to fund early career research and providing mentorship, the Association would become a crucial support structure to financially help GLAM professionals and academic ECRs and to better connect with the wider DH community outside of their home organization or institution. If Fellows were asked to provide a virtual training or workshop as part of their tenure, such as the [CDH Methods Fellowship](#), that could also help fulfill the community's requests for educational opportunities, without the need to develop a full course at this point in the Association's maturity. If this level of funding is unavailable, a Fellowship programme [modeled after the RHS's](#), with networking opportunities and perhaps library access or publisher discounts could be beneficial too.

Collaborative Grants

Many Association members and DH practitioners want to collaborate, but time and cost impede the realisation of this goal. Small grants to concretely support collaborative research efforts are of great interest to the community (in response to survey Question 26). This could either be accomplished through paired fellowships or grants targeting collaborative projects. It would offer a particularly elegant way to connect the DH community, as the terms of the grant could require collaboration between the UK and Ireland or between practitioners at both GLAM and HEI institutions or both. Whether the funding was large enough to support a major project or small enough to supplement other successful grant applications and support researchers as stipendiary bursaries, funding will encourage more collaborative research and more connectivity throughout the DH community.

Community Growth Through Publications

The most popular suggestion for the Association's support of community growth was through direct lobbying with the government for funding and visibility (Question 27). In pursuit of this goal, I prepared a promotional report informed by recommendations from members of the AHRC.

The report highlighted the work of Professor Sally Bushell of Lancaster University, whose AHRC funded Litcraft project uses Minecraft as a platform for

literacy education. The report was titled 'Litcraft: Accessible Experiential Literary Education using Minecraft' and featured quotes from Bushell and Stella Wisdom, Head of Contemporary British and Irish Publications at The British Library. It was written following a review of Litcraft's publicly available materials and an asynchronous virtual interview with Professor Bushell. The report was designed to be short, colourful, and easily skimmable to support wide dissemination.

While the success of the report to garner governmental support is unproven as of yet, its development was relatively

streamlined and the production of similar reports could provide multifaceted opportunities for community engagement as the Association matures. Ideally, the Association could employ a marketing and advocacy fellow to develop similar reports and lobby funders, however this may be out of reach at this stage in the Association's growth. Alternatively, reports might be commissioned by the

Association and written by its members using pre-existing graphical templates. Reports could be published if and when they were developed and could provide:

- **Publicization of engaging research in the field** without the need to operate a dedicated Association journal or publication with a regimented schedule (in response to survey Question 26).
- **Writing and networking opportunities** for students and early career researchers to interview established researchers and learn about a variety of research and collaboration styles.
- **Highlight the value of DH research** to local communities and beyond, expanding definitions of research success beyond publications.
- **Include more GLAM research** into community awareness.

An alternative strategy for lobbying and advocacy would be a more reactive approach. The Association could provide evidence to committees and select committees in the British Parliament and Irish Oireachtas when appropriate, such as the current calls for [the use of Artificial Intelligence and EdTech in Education](#) and the [Regulation of Artificial Intelligence in Ireland](#). Additionally, the Association could publish public statements, as the [RHS does](#), in support of at-risk departments and research programmes, however this strategy is slightly more reactive and defensive than focused on community growth.

Whichever path the UK-IE DH Association takes to grow and support their community, there is optimism in this landscape. Despite the persistent threats and funding cuts facing humanities and cultural heritage organizations, DH is driven by generous and brilliant practitioners. The more folks the Association can help connect and identify with that community, the richer it will be.

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Appendix A: UK-IE DH Association Advocacy and Engagement Survey 2025-26

Bookmarks: [Information Sheet](#), [Participant Consent Form](#), [You and Your Institution](#), [Roles and Collaboration](#), [Advocacy and You](#), [Followups and Interviews](#)

Participation Information Sheet:

Welcome to this advocacy survey, organised by the [UK-Ireland Digital Humanities Association](#) and hosted by the University of London's School of Advanced Study (SAS). You have been invited to take part in this survey because you undertake Digital Humanities work in Ireland and/or in the UK.

The purpose of this survey is to highlight opportunities for advocacy by the UK-Ireland Digital Humanities Association to support both inter-institutional collaboration and individual career growth.

Respondents will be asked to answer anonymous survey questions. Completing this survey will take approximately 15 minutes. No respondents will be financially compensated for their answers. All survey data will be processed according to the General Data Protection Regulations (GDPR). Participation in the research is completely voluntary and participants are at liberty to withdraw at any time without prejudice or negative consequences. Non-participation will not affect anyone's rights or access to future UK-Ireland Digital Humanities Association events or support.

The researchers do not anticipate any potential risks or harms to respondents; the resulting advocacy for the Digital Humanities community should provide benefits to respondents in the form of more specific advocacy support.

The anonymised survey data will be used as evidence for a forthcoming advocacy report and as inspiration for a discussion and guided workshop at the UK-IE Digital Humanities Association's Annual Event on 17 June, 2025 in Glasgow. Some excerpts from long-response answers may be included in reports following the survey, however respondents will not be identified in any published materials beyond their country, institution type, and career stage.

The survey data will be anonymised, however if respondents are willing to be subsequently digitally interviewed about their experiences, or contacted with regard to participation in the 17 June, 2025 workshop, there will be a place for you to include your name and email address. Further consent forms will be provided for

those optional engagements and if you indicate now that you would like to participate and later decide that you would like to withdraw, there will be no prejudice or negative consequences.

All policies and procedures are available here:

<https://www.sas.ac.uk/research/research-office/research-ethics>

PRIVACY NOTICE

The University of London's researchers collect data as part of a formal academic research project. This is governed by the University's academic policies and procedures and our Research Ethics committee. The Research Participant Consent Form should explain to you fully what will happen to your data. Please contact your researcher if you are unsure about anything.

There are broadly two types of data that will collect during the project:

- *data collected in interviews or surveys and used in the research*
- *contact details and relevant forms used to manage the research project*

Our legal basis for processing your data is necessary for a task carried out in the public interest, in this case for the purpose of expanding advocacy for the UK-Ireland Digital Humanities Association. We will not collect special category data as part of this research.

After the research project has been completed the data may be retained and re-used. In some cases it will be added to a data repository for use by other researchers. We, and other academic bodies, are required by law to put in place adequate safeguards to protect your data and your identity (e.g. by anonymising the data or replacing names with other identifiers).

Unless otherwise stated, the University of London is the data controller for the data collected in research projects. We are subject to the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and UK Data Protection Act 2018. You can find out more about data protection at the University, including the contact details the University's data protection officer on the University's website (simply put 'data protection' into the search box or go to the following link:

<https://london.ac.uk/about-us/how-university-run/policies/data-protection>).

For any contact at Institutional level, please address your correspondence to

Research Services, University of London

E: Research.ethics@sas.ac.uk

Tel: 0207 862 8825 | Fax: 0207 862 8657

For specific project questions, please address your correspondence to

Claire Carroll

Advocacy and Engagement Fellow, UK-Ireland DH Association

E: cec205@cam.ac.uk

Section 1: Participant Consent Form

Participants to the research are asked to confirm their participation as follows:

1. I have: *(please tick all)*

read the information about the research/study.

had an opportunity to ask questions and discuss this study

received satisfactory answers to all my questions

received enough information about this study

been given the contact details of the researcher and the Research Services should they need further advice or information

2. I: *(please tick as appropriate)*

Agree to participate in this survey in connection with research being conducted by Claire Carroll in connection with work for the UK-Ireland Digital Humanities Association as explained in the Participation Information Sheet.

Understand that the survey will take about fifteen minutes to complete.

Am free to withdraw from the survey at any time (or until such date as this will no longer be possible, which I have been told), without giving a reason for withdrawing, and without penalty, prejudice, or negative consequences.

Understand that some material from long-response answers may be anonymously quoted in the workshops, papers, and/or reports resulting from this survey.

Understand that at the conclusion of this particular study the tape and transcript of the interview will be kept in the School of Advanced Study and that the completed report will be kept for public use by the University of London

3. Please provide the date in lieu of a signature below:

Short Answer Text

Section 2: You and Your Institution

4. Where are you based?

Ireland

The United Kingdom

Elsewhere

5. Are you currently affiliated with one or more institutions?

Yes

No

6. What is the type of your primary institution?

Higher Education Institution (HEI)

Cultural Heritage Institution (GLAM)

Other

7. If you are affiliated with any institutions in a secondary capacity, please indicate that here.

Higher Education Institution (HEI)

Cultural Heritage Institution (GLAM)

Research Institution (other than HEI)

Creative or Cultural industry/business

Data Science industry/business

Other

8. Do you consider and describe the work that you do under the umbrella of Digital Humanities?

Yes

Sometimes

No

9. Would your institution(s) consider and describe the work that you do under the umbrella of Digital Humanities?

Yes

Sometimes

No

10. Do you find the label of Digital Humanities useful? Why or why not?

Long Answer Text

Section 3: Roles and Collaboration

11. Which of these domains do you have experience in?

digital history methods

digital mapping

TEI/text analysis

data and information literacy

history of technology

digital archiving

AI applications in the humanities

digital media theory

multimedia digital art

computer vision

media infrastructures

algorithmic justice

social network analysis

coding

Other

12. How would you describe your career stage?

student

early career (assistant/junior)

mid-career (curator/engineer/professor)

late career (director/titled/tenured)

emeritus/retired

13. How do you currently find out about upcoming opportunities and jobs?

Long Answer Text

14. What are the strengths/weaknesses of this current method for role visibility?

Long Answer Text

15. What social media platforms do you engage with?

LinkedIn

X/Twitter

Bluesky

Facebook

Other

16. How do you engage with collaboration in your work? Is this a regular part of your role?

This can refer to shared projects inside and outside of your organization.

Long Answer Text

17. Are you/your institution open to collaborating with external researchers?

e.g. folks from other GLAM institutions or HEI researchers.

Yes

No

Other

18. What attributes do you look for in a potential collaborator?

Long Answer Text

19. What tools or platforms do you use to support collaboration?

e.g. Trello, Jira, ActiveCollab etc.

Long Answer Text

20. Are you interested in engaging in more collaborative projects?

Yes

No

Other

21. Is there anything else that you would like to add?

Long Answer Text

Section 4: Advocacy and You

22. Are you a member of any associations or organizations that promote your needs as a Digital Humanities professional?

Yes

No

Other

23. What do you think the strengths/weaknesses of associations are for addressing your needs?

Long Answer Text

24. Are you involved in any advocacy or networking groups?

I am a member of multiple advocacy or networking groups

I am a member of an advocacy or networking group

I would like to be a member of an advocacy or networking group, but am not aware of any available to me

I am not a member of an advocacy or networking group

Other

25. What do you think the strengths/weaknesses of advocacy & networking groups are for addressing your needs?

Long Answer Text

26. How can the UK-Ireland Digital Humanities Association best support your work?

Please add any additional ideas, comments, or clarifications in the 'Other' option.

Provide small grants to encourage inter-institution collaboration

Provide technical support (or connect me with RSEs)

Offer a forum to publicize or publish your work

Advocate for the value of Digital Humanities research and teaching

Host networking events

Promote training opportunities

Provide certification for skills relevant to future employment

Offer training on marketing skills to apply for roles in a new institution/industry

Highlight alternative or non-traditional career paths through published case studies

Host short courses on relevant skill acquisition (and give teaching opportunities)

Other

27. How do you think the UK-Ireland Digital Humanities Association can best support the growth of the community as a whole?

Please add any additional ideas, comments, or clarifications in the 'Other' option.

Facilitate training around community organizing

Improve awareness through public-facing interest-group coalitions

Directly lobby with government organizations for funding and visibility

Supporting extra-curricular practices and mental health awareness

Other

28. Is there anything else that you would like to add?

Long Answer Text

Section 5: Followups and Interviews

29. If you are interested in potentially being interviewed about your responses in pursuit of improved advocacy through the Association, please provide your name below.

Short Answer Text

30. If you are interested in being interviewed, please provide your email address.

Short Answer Text

Thank You

Thank you for participating in this survey. If you'd like to keep informed about the results of this research and/or the UK-Ireland DH Association and its work, you can subscribe to the mailing list [here](#).

If you have any questions about this project, please feel free to reach out to Claire Carroll at cec205@cam.ac.uk.

Appendix B: UK-IE DH Association Advocacy and Engagement Survey 2025-26 Quantitative Results

Question 1: I have: (please tick all)

(50/50 respondents)

Choice	Responses	%
Read the information about the research/study	50	100%
Had the opportunity to ask questions and discuss this study	50	100%
Received satisfactory answers to all my questions	50	100%
Received enough information about this study	50	100%
Been given the contact details of the researcher and the Research Services should they need further advice or information	50	100%

Question 2: I: (please tick as appropriate)

(50/50 respondents)

Choice	Responses	%
Agree to participate in this survey in connection with research being conducted by Claire Carroll in connection with work for the UK-Ireland Digital Humanities Association as explained in the Participation Information Sheet.	50	100%
Understand that the survey will take about fifteen minutes to complete.	50	100%
Am free to withdraw from the survey at any time (or until such date as this will no longer be possible, which I have been told), without giving a reason for withdrawing, and without penalty, prejudice, or negative consequences.	50	100%
Understand that some material from long-response answers may be anonymously quoted in the workshops, papers, and/or reports resulting from this survey.	50	100%
Understand that at the conclusion of this particular study the tape and transcript of the interview will be kept in the School of Advanced Study and that the completed report will be kept for public use by the University of London.	50	100%

Question 4: Where are you based?

(50/50 respondents)

Choice	Responses	%
Ireland	10	20%
The United Kingdom	38	76%
Elsewhere	2	4%

Question 5: Are you currently affiliated with one or more institutions?

(50/50 respondents)

Choice	Responses	%
Yes	45	90%
No	5	10%

Question 6: What is the type of your primary institution?

(50/50 respondents)

Choice	Responses	%
Higher Education Institution (HEI)	40	80%
Cultural Heritage Institution (GLAM)	9	18%
Other	1	2%

Question 7: If you are affiliated with any institutions in a secondary capacity, please indicate that here

(22/50 respondents)

Choice	Responses	%
Higher Education Institution (HEI)	12	54.55%
Cultural Heritage Institution (GLAM)	6	27.27%
Research Institution (other than HEI)	1	4.55%
Creative or Cultural industry/business	4	18.18%
Data Science industry/business	0	0%
Other	4	18.18%

Question 8: Do you consider and describe the work that you do under the umbrella of Digital Humanities?

(50/50 respondents)

Choice	Responses	%
Yes	35	70%
Sometimes	14	28%
No	1	2%

Question 9: Would your institution(s) consider and describe the work that you do under the umbrella of Digital Humanities?

(50/50 respondents)

Choice	Responses	%
Yes	34	68%
Sometimes	13	26%
No	3	6%

Question 11: Which of these domains do you have experience in?

(45/50 respondents)

Choice	Responses	%
Digital history methods	23	51.11%
Digital mapping	20	44.44%
TEI/text analysis	20	44.44%
Data and information literacy	30	66.67%
History of technology	19	42.22%
Digital archiving	24	53.33%
AI applications in the humanities	24	53.33%
Digital media theory	12	26.67%
Multimedia digital art	4	8.89%
Computer vision	10	22.22%
Media infrastructures	9	20%

Algorithmic justice	7	15.56%
Social network analysis	21	46.67%
coding	27	60%
Other	11	24.44%

Question 12: How would you describe your career stage?

(45/50 respondents)

Choice	Responses	%
Student	4	8.89%
Early career (Assistant/junior)	10	22.22%
Mid-career (curator/engineer/professor)	22	48.89%
Late career (director/titled/tenured)	9	20%
emeritus/retired	0	0%

Question 15: What social media platforms do you engage with?

(45/50 respondents)

Choice	Responses	%
LinkedIn	33	73.33%
X/Twitter	4	8.89%
Bluesky	21	46.67%
Facebook	12	26.67%
Other	016	35.56%

**Question 17: Are you/your institution open to collaborating with external researchers?
E.g. folks from other GLAM institutions or HEI researchers.**

(45/50 respondents)

Choice	Responses	%
Yes	44	97.78%

No	1	2.22%
Other	0	0%

Question 20: Are you interested in engaging in more collaborative projects?

(45/50 respondents)

Choice	Responses	%
Yes	41	91.11%
No	2	4.44%
Other	2	4.44%

Question 22: Are you a member of any associations or organizations that promote your needs as a Digital Humanities professional?

(44/50 respondents)

Choice	Responses	%
Yes	23	52.27%
No	19	43.18%
Other	2	4.55%

Question 24: Are you involved in any advocacy or networking groups?

(43/50 respondents)

Choice	Responses	%
I am a member of multiple advocacy or networking groups	14	32.56%
I am a member of an advocacy or networking group	2	4.65%
I would like to be a member of an advocacy or networking group, but am not aware of any available to me	9	20.93%
I am not a member of an advocacy or networking group	17	39.53%
Other	1	2.33%

Question 26: How can the UK-Ireland Digital Humanities Association best support your work? Please add any additional ideas, comments, or clarifications in the 'Other' option.

(44/50 respondents)

Choice	Responses	%
Provide small grants to encourage inter-institution collaboration	27	61.36%
Provide technical support (or connect me with RSEs)	16	36.36%
Offer a forum to publicize or publish your work	19	43.18%
Advocate for the value of Digital Humanities research and teaching	31	70.45%
Host networking events	30	68.18%
Promote training opportunities	31	70.45%
Provide certification for skills relevant to future employment	7	15.91%
Offer training on marketing skills to apply for roles in a new institution/industry	6	13.64%
Highlight alternative or non-traditional career paths through published case studies	23	52.27%
Host short courses on relevant skill acquisition (and give teaching opportunities)	21	47.73%
Other	6	13.64%

Question 27: How do you think the UK-Ireland Digital Humanities Association can best support the growth of the community as a whole? Please add any additional ideas, comments, or clarifications in the 'Other' option.

(41/50 respondents)

Choice	Responses	%
Facilitate training around community organizing	19	46.34%
Improve awareness through public-facing interest-group coalitions	23	56.10%
Directly lobby with government organizations for funding and visibility	27	65.85%
Supporting extra-curricular practices and mental health awareness	7	17.07%
Other	6	14.63%

